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The Arrival and Dissemination of Islamic Sciences in Mekran: A Research Review

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Abstract

Mekran, an ancient and historically significant region, is closely linked to Prophet Noah's grandson, who settled in the area. The region gained further prominence during the era of Caliph Umar (RA) when it was conquered by his companions, marking the beginning of Islam's widespread acceptance among its inhabitants. This Islamic influence has continued over the centuries. Mekran holds a special place in Islamic scholarship, particularly in the fields of Tafseer (Quranic exegesis) and Hadith. Its contribution to Islamic knowledge is immense, as it was home to some of the earliest scholars in these areas. Among these scholars was Allama Abd bin Hamid, who is credited with writing the first known book on Tafseer and Hadith. His work, rooted in the "Kas" region of Mekran, further solidified the area's academic significance. The legacy of Mekran in Islamic intellectual history remains noteworthy to this day, especially for its early contributions to the study of Islamic texts.

Keywords: Mekran, Prophet Noah (PBUH), Conquest of Mekran, Abd bin Hamid, Tafseer of Abd bin Hamid

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